

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Recommendations for the use of undersowing in organic potato production in the continental region

Increasing infestation rates from soilborne and mycotoxin-producing plant pathogenic fungi such as *Fusarium* and *Alternaria* pose major challenges for organic potato cultivation in the continental region. Current control measures combine copper-containing contact fungicides with intensive tillage, which has a negative long-term effect on soil health. In terms of alternative strategies, bioregulation by fungivorous soil animals (e.g., collembolans, mites) represents a promising approach. These antagonists can reduce infestation and mycotoxin loads. In order to optimally use this ecosystem service, management adaptations are required that promote bioregulation and allow for fungicide reduction. In this context, in a case study, it was investigated to what extent the cultivation of undersown plants represents such a suitable adjustment. Two undersowing techniques were compared: strip undersowing (only in furrows)

and broad undersowing (across furrows and ridges). Based on the results, the promotion of the cultivation of undersown plants in organic potato cultivation is recommended in order to improve soil conditions and foster antagonists (soil animals, saprotrophic fungi) and their services (e.g., bioregulation). From an agro-ecological perspective, positive effects on soil biodiversity can be expected in the year of cultivation. Long-term effects are unlikely with conventional tillage. From an agro-economic point of view, it is important to ensure that the undersowing does not compete with the crop in order to avoid negative effects on yields and profitability. Further studies on the suitability of different undersowing mixes are recommended. Broad undersowing should generally be preferred over strip undersowing.

1. Undersow mix (*Vicia sativa*, *Linum usitatissimum*, *Lolium perenne*, *Trifolium resupinatum*, *Guizotia abyssinica*) in organic potato production on the experimental field.

KEYWORDS

Organic potato cultivation, undersowing, bioregulation, plant pathogenic fungi, soil fauna

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

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